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Multilevel resistive switching in nano silver incorporated Chitosan thin films

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Introduction

Recent advances in polymer nano composite based resistive switching memory ReRAM devices has opened up a huge research potential in the possible biodegradable polymer nano composite based ReRAM devices . This field is fast expanding as biodegradable memory devices would be environmental friendly, easy and cost effective fabrication processes and more interestingly the physics behind the resistive switching itself is intriguing.

Biodegradable organic materials used for nonvolatile memory application that are based on resistive switching phenomenon known as ReRAM have many advantages namely, more memory storage, flexibility, in some cases transparent, simple fabrication processes and low cost etc. In this work we report on the usage of Chitosan flakes with high molecular weight(Mol.Wt 4000) incorporated directly with silver nanoparticles for the fabrication of resistive switching memory element.

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Chitosan flakes with high molecular weight (Mol. Wt 4000) was purchased from Sigma Aldrich company. Silver nanoparticles with 99% purity of size <math>< 150\text{nm}</math> was used for dispersion in Chitosan film. Initially 1 wt% Chitosan solution was prepared. 5.2 mg of silver nanoparticles was added to 10ml of chitosan solution and ultrasonicated for 15 min until the silver nanoparticles are completely in chitosan solution. Few drops of solution are placed on ultra clean ITO for making the first thin film. The ITO is placed on Spin coater holder and spun at 300 rpm for 10sec. The ITO is then dried at 60°C . For making second chitosan film, another ITO was used and spin coated the solution at the same speed. Once it is dried at 60°C another layer was spin coated with the solution to form two layers. Silver paste is used as top electrode for Electrical characterization.

Fig.1 Multilevel resistive switching in nano silver incorporated chitosan thin films

Fig .1 shows multilevel switching characteristics of the chitosan and silver film for one layer. The resistive switching is cycle dependent. The first switching occurred at 3.5V. As the number of cycles are increased the switching voltage decreases with increasing ON/OFF voltage. We can also observe multilevel switching in few cycles from HRS to LRS. The retention time at LRS is stable for more than 1000 sec .

Conclusion

For the first time in the chitosan with silver doped system, we have observed stable multiresistive switching of ON/OFF ratio of more than 4 orders. This clearly shows that the chitosan system can be used for practical applications